
Deliverable D1.3

First Project activity, including Governance report

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Author(s):	Anne Fouilloux (LWE)
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Abstract:	This deliverable summarises FAIR2Adapt activities and governance during its first reporting period (M1–M12, 2025), reviewing progress across all seven work packages and defining priorities for Year 2. Year 1 built a strong foundation for FAIR implementation across six case studies through targeted capacity building, transforming initial uncertainty into readiness. While FAIR understanding is now in place, communities do not yet clearly see the practical value of FAIR Digital Objects, as technical developments progressed in parallel with onboarding. Year 2 will therefore focus on FAIR in practice, demonstrating concrete benefits through co-design, demonstrators, dashboards, and solution pathways linking stakeholder needs to technical services.
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Editor(s):	Anne Fouilloux (LWE), Alexandra Garatzogianni (TIB), Michael Fribus (TIB), Raul Palma (PSNC), Esteban Gonzalez (UPM), Barbara Magagna (GFF), Riccardo Iannotta (ALPHA), Zakieh Alizadehsani (TIB), Christine Matauschek (FTC)
Reviewer(s):	Inês Gomes Marques (FC.ID)
Internally approved by:	Anne Fouilloux (LWE)
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Terms and Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CCA	Climate Change Adaptation
CS	Case Study
DGGS	Discrete Global Grid System
EAB	External Advisory Board
EBM	Executive Board Meeting
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDO	FAIR Digital Objects
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
GA	General Assembly
HE	Horizon Europe
LWE	LifeWatch ERIC
MS	Milestone
PC	Project Coordinator

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
AI	Artificial Intelligence
RI	Research Infrastructure
RO	Research Objects
SIP	Semantic Interoperability Profile
STAC	Spatio-Temporal Asset Catalog
TWG	Thematic Working Group for Climate Change Adaptation
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a comprehensive report on the FAIR2Adapt project activities, outcomes, and governance during its first year (M1–M12, January–December 2025). It covers administrative, technical, and governance activities, as well as risk management and quality assurance procedures, with a systematic assessment of progress across all seven work packages.

Year 1 successfully laid the foundation for FAIR implementation across all six case study communities: stakeholder workshops were completed, FAIR awareness training and capacity building delivered, the first versions of the FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) finalised, and the FAIRification Framework API specification (MS3.1) developed. An External Advisory Board was established, and a key personnel risk was mitigated through the LifeWatch partnership. A joint Thematic Working Group on CCA data management was prepared with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC and approved by MIP4Adapt. The project established visibility through participation in key conferences (EGU, EGI Conference, ECCA) including joint activities with our sister project CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC.

While communities now understand FAIR principles and are ready to engage with implementation, the practical benefits of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) are not yet fully demonstrated. Year 2 will focus on moving from FAIR readiness (e.g. understanding the FAIR principles) to FAIR in practice, linking stakeholder questions to technical outputs through co-design sessions, demonstrators, iterative dashboards, and solution pathways.

The project is on track, with no major delays and only two minor milestone adjustments (MS5.4 - SIPs, and MS7.3 - TWG) with no impact on the overall timeline.

1. Introduction

1.1 Project Context

FAIR2Adapt addresses the challenge of enabling European regional and local authorities to build resilience against climate change impacts through improved knowledge sharing and reuse. The project consortium comprises 17 partners from 13 countries, including research institutions, technology providers, and SMEs, working together to leverage the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) for climate change adaptation.

The project places FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) at the centre of its technical architecture, utilising RO-Crate as the primary implementation standard supported by Nanopublications and ROHub as the management platform. This approach enables standardised representation, exchange, and discovery of research products while ensuring alignment with EOSC interoperability requirements.

1.2 Work Package Structure

The project is organised into seven work packages. Table 1 summarises the structure and Year 1 status.

Table 1: Work Package Overview

WP	Title	Lead	Status
WP1	Project Management, Coordination, Governance	SRL→LWE	On Track
WP2	Core FDO Infrastructure	PSNC	On Track
WP3	FDO-driven FAIRification Framework	UPM	On Track
WP4	User-facing Knowledge Services for CCA	TIB	On Track
WP5	Community Support and Engagement	GFF	On Track
WP6	Case Studies and End-user Applications	FCID	On Track
WP7	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation	ALPHA	On Track

1.3 Year 1 Objectives

The first reporting period focused on establishing the foundation for FAIR implementation through four primary objectives:

1. **Infrastructure establishment:** Implementation of governance structures, communication channels, and technical infrastructure;
2. **Capacity building:** Comprehensive training programme including FAIR awareness, FIP/SIP development, and M4M workshops;
3. **Requirements analysis:** Systematic elicitation of stakeholder requirements through user story methodology;

4. **Technical specification:** Definition of FAIRification framework and initial RO-Crate profiles.

2. Administrative Activities

2.1 Project Setup and Kick-off

The FAIR2Adapt project officially started on 1 January 2025. The kick-off meeting was held in January 2025 (13-15 January 2025), followed by the first case study workshop (CS2 - RiOMar, 16-19 January 2025). This first workshop allowed us to align on project objectives while immediately engaging with practical case study work, laying the ground for future case study workshops.

Key setup activities completed:

- Consortium Agreement signed by all partners
- Financial identification collected from all partners
- Internal communication tools established (Mattermost, Google Drive, Zoom)
- Helpdesk operational (f2a-helpdesk@simula.no and online platform available at <https://fair2adapt.github.io/fair2adapt-helpdesk>)
- Project Handbook (D1.1) delivered in M3 (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15130761](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15130761))
- Data Management Plan (D1.2) delivered in M6 (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.16901205](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16901205))

2.2 Financial Management

Pre-financing was distributed to all project partners according to the Grant Agreement. Budget monitoring procedures have been established and are being followed by all partners. Several changes requiring Grant Agreement amendment have been approved by the General Assembly during Year 1:

- Addition of LifeWatch ERIC (LWE) as new partner with transfer of coordination budget from Simula Research Laboratory
- Withdrawal of Simula Research Laboratory
- Subcontract for SEI-Oxford for taxonomy development work

A formal Grant Agreement amendment request will be submitted to the European Commission in January 2026. Project activities continue uninterrupted during the amendment process.

2.3 Consortium Changes

During Year 1, significant consortium changes occurred following the departure of the coordinator to LifeWatch ERIC (Spain) and Simula Research Laboratory's decision to withdraw from the project at M11:

1. **Departure of the FAIR2Adapt coordinator from Simula Research Laboratory to LifeWatch ERIC:** Anne Fouilloux resigned from her position at Simula Research

Laboratory to get a new job at LifeWatch ERIC (Spain). As a consequence, a first Extraordinary General Assembly (28 October 2025) unanimously approved the incorporation of LifeWatch ERIC as a new FAIR2Adapt partner.

2. **Withdrawal of Simula Research Laboratory and Transfer of Coordination to LifeWatch ERIC to be established:** Simula Research Laboratory decided to withdraw from the consortium. Following this decision, a second Extraordinary General Assembly (24 November 2025) approved transferring full coordination responsibilities, including Administrative, Financial, and Technical Coordination, to LifeWatch ERIC. Anne Fouilloux continues as the Coordinator of FAIR2Adapt at LWE, ensuring continuity of project leadership. A formal withdrawal letter has been submitted to the EC in December 2025, with the Grant Agreement amendment process commencing in January 2026.
3. **Addition of subcontract for SEI-Oxford:** The taxonomy used by the Connectivity Hub and weADAPT (developed during the MAIA project) has been identified as a key resource for the CCA community. SEI-Oxford requested to subcontract some technical work related to this taxonomy. This was approved unanimously by all partners present at the General Assembly on 28 October 2025.

3. Technical Activities Summary

3.1 WP2 - Core FDO Infrastructure

Lead: PSNC | Status: On Track

What was done

WP2 has established regular bi-weekly meetings since February 2025. Key achievements include:

- **T2.1** - Metadata schema work progressed across all 6 case studies.
 - Stakeholder workshops conducted in June 2025 to elicit metadata requirements.
 - CS2 (Biscayan RiOMar) metadata schema mapping finalised (November 2025), aligning case study needs with standard vocabularies and metadata models (e.g., schema.org , (Geo)-DCAT)
 - Follow-up discussions (email and one-to-one meetings) held with case study partners to validate metadata coverage and expected values.
 - Alignment work carried out between domain standards and RO-Crate metadata, including STAC, ISO 191XX, GeoDCAT-AP, NetCDF, and Zarr, using schema.org and profile extensions.
- **T2.2** – RO-Crate profile development ongoing, contributing to MS2.1 (M12).
 - An abstract on our implementation of FAIR Digital Objects using RO-Crate profiles and nanopublications for climate change adaptation was submitted and accepted at the FDO Conference 2026.
- **T2.3** – ROHub improvements and extensions implemented to support FAIR2Adapt needs, including:
 - customizable visual components to display resource metadata in the portal;
 - updated support for the latest RO-Crate specification (v1.2);

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- implementation of the Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) to enable harvesting of RO-Crates from external SKGs (e.g. OpenAIRE/EOSC).
- **T2.4** – EarthQA engine improvements for natural language search initiated.
- Ongoing extensions and adaptation of EarthQA service to leverage RO-Crate metadata (obtained via ROHub) in the search and discovery operations.
- **T2.5** – Interoperability improvements in ROHub, including:
 - implementation of a storage microservice to connect multiple storage backends;
 - preparation for integration of an updated semantic enrichment service;
 - preparation for integration of a FAIR assessment tool based on the FAIR-IF specification and RO-Crate v1.2;
 - initial work on leveraging the new EOSC AAI (nodes ecosystem).
- **T2.6** – Infrastructure operational via PSNC, preparing resources for the deployment of other services like semantic enrichment, leveraging existing EOSC resources (e.g., storage, notebooks) and ongoing discussion on missing resources.

What we learned

While metadata standards and RO-Crate profiles can be defined at a technical level, case study communities struggled to relate these artefacts to their concrete questions and decision-making needs: for example, understanding how an RO-Crate profile would help them identify relevant adaptation measures for urban heat mitigation or structure their municipal adaptation strategy. Parallel technical development and community onboarding were necessary due to project timing, but delayed validation of technical outputs from a user perspective. This highlighted the need to reposition ROHub not merely as a technical repository, but as a central registry that aggregates RO-Crates produced by multiple FAIR2Adapt and external services (such as ORKG and DeSci Publish), enabling downstream automation, discovery, and assessment.

What this enables next

WP2 will shift from infrastructure and specification development to demonstrators that explicitly connect stakeholder questions to RO-Crate-based services. ROHub will be used as the integration point for RO-Crates generated across FAIR2Adapt and EOSC services, supporting automatic metadata enrichment, FAIR assessment, and discovery through EarthQA. In Year 2, demonstrators (GA in March 2026) will first showcase ROHub as a collaborative platform supporting the research lifecycle, with service integration following in later phases.

3.2 WP3 - FDO-driven FAIRification Framework

Lead: UPM | Status: On Track

What was done

WP3 has held monthly meetings since February 2025. The work focused on defining a stages pipeline to transform climate adaptation resources into FAIR Digital Objects, following

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an approach similar to the Software Development Lifecycle (analysis → design → implementation → testing/deployment).

Key achievements include:

1. **T3.1** – FAIRification Framework:
 - a. MS3.1 achieved (M6): FAIRification Framework API specification published at <https://w3id.org/fff>
 - b. D3.1 FAIRification Framework document delivered (M12, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18110239](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18110239))
 - c. Services characterisation completed, defining interactions between FAIR Assessment, I-ADOPT, metadata extraction, and other services
 - d. Four showcases defined for demonstrating FAIR solutions at the General Assembly in March 2026
 - e. Joint workshop with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC at EGI Conference (June 2025) to align FDO approaches
2. **T3.2** – FAIR Assessment service:
 - a. FAIR Assessment Tool workshop held (October 2025)
 - b. [Metrics](#) identified for assessing digital objects against FAIR principles
 - c. Preparation for customisation based on community FIPs
 - d. Metrics and tests compatible with the [FAIR Assessment Interoperability Framework](#) defined in the project OSTRAILS
3. **T3.3** – Automated I-ADOPT service:
 - a. Preliminary application of LLMs to generate machine-readable variable descriptions
 - b. Evaluation dataset built from I-ADOPT challenge, comprising 100 agreed variable representations. A paper describing this work has been submitted to the Semantic Web Journal.
 - c. Pattern library for selecting decomposition approach in development
4. **T3.4** – AI-supported information extraction service:
 - a. Base implementation of metadata extraction services available via API, currently in use by ROHub
 - b. Capabilities include topic/keyword/entity extraction, salient sentence detection, and scientific claims extraction
 - c. Discussion with PSNC on factorisation between document-level and FDO-level enrichment
5. **T3.5** – FAIR data publishing pipeline (DeSci Publish):
 - a. Workshop held for all teams on DeSci Publish platform
 - b. RO-Crate implementation upgraded to meet latest specification (v1.2)
 - c. Integration of FAIROs FAIRification tests in progress
 - d. Bug fixes contributed to F-UJI tool; pull request submitted to expand PID recognition beyond DOI

What we learned

The FAIRification Framework requires careful separation between document-level enrichment (extracting metadata from publications) and FDO-level enrichment (enhancing the FAIR Digital Object itself). Discussions with PSNC clarified this factorisation, which still needs to be fully implemented. Additionally, while the framework defines clear stages and services, communities needed more guidance on which services apply to their specific digital objects and how to sequence FAIRification activities. The 3-Point FAIRification Framework (FIP, M4M, FAIR Orchestration) provides a useful conceptual structure, but applying it requires significant expert supervision—highlighting the importance of the co-design approach planned for Year 2.

What this enables next

Year 2 will focus on implementing FAIRification plans for each case study, moving from framework definition to practical application. The first four showcases (planned for the GA in March 2026) will demonstrate how the framework services work together to transform case study resources into validated FDOs. Services will be progressively integrated into ROHub (D2.1 at M21), enabling automated FAIR assessment, I-ADOPT variable annotation, and metadata enrichment as part of the standard FAIRification workflow.

3.3 WP4 - User-facing Knowledge Services

Lead: TIB | Status: On Track

What was done

WP4 holds bi-weekly meetings (2nd and 4th Wednesdays). The work package translates user requirements from case studies into concrete service specifications for data analysis, knowledge synthesis, and dashboard-based publishing. Key achievements include:

- **T4.1** – FDO Services interfaces for data handling:
 - Case studies presented their data handling needs in WP4 meetings
 - Use Case description table template developed for dashboards and services
 - Groundwork laid for FDO integration in computing environments (Python, R, Excel, Jupyter, QGIS)
- **T4.2** – FDO Services for transdisciplinary knowledge synthesis:
 - Knowledge Loom (ORKG-based) work initiated with CS3 (Hamburg) and CS4 (Portugal)
 - Knowledge Loom article prepared for systematic review supporting weADAPT
 - Approach defined for harvesting structured knowledge from FDOs and interlinking via nanopublications
- **T4.3** – Multilingual generative question answering:
 - Requirements gathered from case studies for question-answering functionality
 - Coordination with WP3 on integration of LLM-based services for CCA domain
- **T4.4** – Customisable dashboards:

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- Dashboard development initiated for 2 case studies:
 - CS3 Hamburg: integrated urban climate risk assessment, with primary focus on pluvial flood risk mapping combining hazard, exposure and vulnerability data
 - CS6 CCA strategy & plans: FAIRification of climate adaptation strategy, focusing on structured presentation of adaptation measures linked to climate risks, traceability from policy recommendations to underlying evidence, and support for strategy update processes
 - CS4 Portugal: mockup dashboard for the national climate adaptation hub, supporting discovery and access to adaptation knowledge resources, including those derived from systematic reviews
- Dashboard prototypes brainstormed in design thinking workshops (June 2025)
- Task formally starts M18, but early engagement ensured requirements capture
- **MS4.1 achieved (M10):** Draft specifications for Knowledge Services published, translating user requirements into technical system specifications.

What we learned

Translating case study needs into service specifications revealed a disconnect between the Case Study description template for dashboards and the underlying FDO/RO-Crate architecture. Communities expressed their needs in terms of questions and decisions (e.g., "which adaptation measures address specific climate risks?", "what evidence supports this policy recommendation?"), but the current template does not systematically link these needs to the RO-Crate profiles that would enable answering them. Dashboard prototyping proved effective for eliciting what stakeholders want to see, but additional work is needed to trace these requirements back to specific metadata fields, vocabularies, and RO-Crate structures. This gap highlights the need for tighter integration between WP4 service specifications, the user requirements captured in WP5 (D5.2), the stocktaking analysis in WP6 (D6.1), and the RO-Crate profile definition in WP2.

What this enables next

Year 2 will focus on reworking and systematising the Case Study description template to explicitly link dashboard requirements to RO-Crate profiles. This will require iterative cycles: starting from stakeholder questions, identifying the data and metadata needed to answer them, mapping these to RO-Crate profile elements, and validating through dashboard prototypes. Close coordination with WP5 (user requirements) and WP6 (case study needs) will ensure alignment across work packages. The alpha release of Knowledge Services (MS4.2, M15) will test initial implementations, with revised specifications (MS4.3, M21) incorporating lessons learned. Dashboard development (T4.4, from M18) will follow two-week iterative cycles, with each cycle refining both the visual outputs and the underlying RO-Crate requirements.

3.4 WP5 - Community Support and Engagement

Lead: GFF | Status: On Track

What was done

WP5 focuses on FAIR capacity building, user requirements elicitation, and community support. Key achievements include:

- **T5.1 – FAIR Capacity Building:**
 - MS5.1 achieved (M2): FAIR Awareness course delivered, with participation documented via nanopublications
 - Training materials developed based on GO FAIR Foundation's Capacity Building Programme
 - Case study stakeholders engaged in FAIR training to prepare them for FIP development
- **T5.2 – User requirements for FAIR and scientifically sound CCA:**
 - D5.2 User Requirements Report delivered (M12, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18110626](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18110626)), documenting the methodology and initial requirements. The deliverable also describes the Digital Objects identified in each case study that are targeted for FAIRification.
 - User story methodology established: "As a [role], I want [action], so that [purpose]" - with specific statements abstracted into generalised terms for cross-case comparison. These user stories are described semantically using nanopublications
 - Stepwise requirement elicitation process defined, involving case study providers, semantic experts (WP3, WP5), and technical experts (WP3, WP4)
 - Four artefact types created in FIP Wizard: Case Study descriptions, User Stories, Digital Object Analysis, and FAIR Implementation Profiles.
 - MS5.3 achieved (M6): FIPs published as nanopublications for all case studies
 - MS5.4 achieved (M9, moved from M6): SIPs published in September 2025. **The delay had no impact on project progress, as communities needed to complete FAIR Awareness training before meaningfully defining semantic interoperability requirements.**
 - Following D5.2 recommendations, **FIPs and SIPs are now aggregated into single extended FIPs** at the case study level, streamlining the approach and avoiding duplication. These extended FIPs serve as the basis for more specialised FIPs at the digital object level.
 - Solution paths identified for each user story: FAIRification, data processing pipelines, transformation to knowledge, dashboards, stakeholder engagement.
- **T5.3 – Community co-development of customised services:**
 - Co-design workshops conducted in June 2025 (jointly with WP6) using design-thinking methodology
 - User stories linked to action plans: FAIRification plan (T3.1), workflow plan (T5.3), knowledge enrichment plan (T4.2), dashboard plan (T4.4), stakeholder engagement plan (T6.1)
- **T5.4 – Helpdesk:**
 - MS5.2 achieved (M2): Helpdesk Guide published online, GitHub repository established
 - Support infrastructure operational for assisting users with FAIR data practices and project services

What we learned

The requirement elicitation process revealed that FAIR is not yet a familiar concept for most case study stakeholders, which justified the SIP milestone adjustment. The decision to integrate SIPs into extended FIPs (rather than maintaining separate profiles) simplifies the workflow and ensures that semantic interoperability considerations are addressed within the same framework as FAIR implementation choices. The user story methodology proved effective for capturing high-level needs, but translating these into concrete technical specifications required significant facilitation by semantic and technical experts. The stepwise process—from case study description to user story to digital object analysis to FIP—provides a structured path, but each step requires careful handoff between contributors. Additionally, the connection between user stories and the RO-Crate profiles that would technically enable them needs to be made more explicit.

What this enables next

Year 2 will focus on executing the action plans derived from user stories, moving from requirements to implemented solutions. The extended FIPs will inform the FAIR Assessment service (T3.2), enabling validation of whether digital objects actually implement the FAIR Supporting Resources the community claims to use. The 1st release of Customised CCA-related Services (D5.3, M18) will deliver initial tools based on the co-development process. Community feedback will drive iterative refinement through hackathons and Open Forums. The Community Capacity Building Report (D5.1, M24) will document training outcomes and participation. The Helpdesk will expand its support as more services become available, guiding communities through FAIRification workflows and FDO creation.

3.5 WP6 - Case Studies and End-user Applications

Lead: FC.ID | Status: On Track

What was done

WP6 tests and validates the FAIR2Adapt framework through six real-world case studies spanning different adaptation contexts, scales, and data challenges. WP6 holds monthly meetings since February 2025. All six case studies completed design thinking stakeholder workshops and FIP/SIP development during Year 1. The table below summarises case-specific highlights at M12:

Table 2: FAIR2Adapt Case Studies

CS	Title	Highlights at M12
CS1	Arctic Radioisotopes	First RO-Crate completed, first nanopublications for CS1 published, can FAIRify autonomously
CS2	RiOMar (Coastal France)	First RO-Crate completed, Data FAIRification flow started, STAC/DGGS-Healpix pipeline started and new hire for stakeholder engagement on data-to-knowledge transformation

CS3	Hamburg City	First RO-Crate completed, pluvial flood risk map under peer review, dashboard mockup initiated, code conversion to Python started
CS4	Portugal National Hub	First RO-Crate completed, systematic review of ~200 resources ongoing, dashboard mockup initiated with WP4, LLM extraction experiments started for research articles, identification of data portals ongoing
CS5	weADAPT/Connectivity Hub	First RO-Crate completed, MAIA taxonomy FAIRification ongoing, SEI-Oxford subcontract requested as the MAIA taxonomy has been identified as key for all case studies
CS6	EU Taxonomy/CCA Strategy	Pivoted to Bremen partnership, FAIRification of CCA strategy

Key WP6 Milestones Achieved:

- MS6.1 (M3): 1st set of case studies workshops completed
- MS6.2 (M7): All 6 case studies defined and started
- **T6.1 – Stock-taking of adaptation data and knowledge needs (M1-M12, Lead: SEI): Task finished**
 - Task completed with submission of D6.1 - Stocktaking of adaptation data and knowledge needs (submitted at the EC portal on the 17th December 2025, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18017945](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18017945))
 - Design-thinking workshops were conducted in June 2025 (jointly with WP5) with a standardised structure across all case studies: stakeholder mapping using metaphor-based archetype cards, process and timeline mapping, dashboard co-design, and metadata/user story elicitation.
 - The End-to-End Adaptation Data Journey framework was developed, mapping the stages from data generation to decision-making and identifying where each case study contributes.
- **T6.2 – From data to knowledge: facilitating search, access and discovery of FAIR data in support of CCA (M6-M36, Lead: FCID): Task ongoing.**
 - Building on T6.1 insights, this task supports the transformation of scientific evidence and local knowledge into FDOs.
 - Case studies are now applying FAIR2Adapt FAIRification frameworks, with RO-Crates and FIPs completed for all case studies, FAIR requirements and CCA- related requirements identified for all case studies, and data FAIRification flows initiated for CS2.
 - WP6 monitoring framework started for all case studies, to allow progress checking on FAIR2Adapt services application
 - The task coordinates with WP2-WP4 for technical implementation and WP5 for community engagement. Case studies receive support from the Helpdesk (T5.4) for FDO creation.

- **T6.3 – Upscale and uptake via EU Mission and EOSC (M18-M36, Lead: FTC): Task not yet started (begins M18).**
 - Preparatory work has commenced through collaboration with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC to identify transfer case opportunities.

CS6 scope change: Case Study 6 moved from its original objective (consulting SMEs on climate risk assessments for EU taxonomy sustainability reporting) to its current scope (FAIRifying the climate adaptation strategy of the city of Bremen for different stakeholder groups). This change was necessitated by amendments in EU regulations (CSRD reporting) that made it difficult to find companies willing to conduct climate risk assessments. The new scope better aligns with FAIR2Adapt objectives: by focusing on communal stakeholders and FAIR adaptation strategies, CS6 now covers several parts of the adaptation cycle and creates stronger synergies with CS4 (Portugal national hub) which faces similar challenges in translating grey literature into machine-readable information. Possible synergies and interlinks were also identified with the city of Graz, which has been identified as a transfer case (Task 6.3).

Synergies with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC: A joint session on '[FAIR data and open science in support of climate change adaptation](#)' was presented at the European Climate Change Adaptation Conference in June 2025 with the sister project CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC, and which marked the beginning of the collaboration with the sister project. Further communications are ongoing between the technical partners from each project, to understand synergies and leverages between FAIR services and FAIRification application. Their three case studies present opportunities for knowledge exchange and potential transfer case development under Task 6.3:

Table 3: CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC Case Studies and Potential Synergies

Case Study	Focus	FAIR2Adapt Synergy
Athens Urban Heat	Just-CURS digital twin; citizen engagement	CS3 Hamburg - urban heat
Portugal Coastal Wetland	OPENHIDRA flood forecasting	CS2 RIOMar, CS4 Portugal
France Clay Shrink-Swell	Space2Earth geotechnical risk	CS6 Bremen - infrastructure

Preparation ground for transfer cases is being developed with FTC, under Task 6.3.

What we learned

The workshops revealed that information needs are not linear or isolated but interdependent, requiring joint reflection between data producers, intermediaries, and users. The End-to-End Adaptation Data Journey framework helped visualise where different case studies contribute and where gaps exist. A key insight from D6.1 is that FAIRification processes must be oriented toward decision-making processes, where data informs and enables action.

The stocktaking process yielded mitigated success across case studies, revealing significant differences in readiness and engagement—but also complementary strengths that can be leveraged in Year 2.

Some case studies demonstrated strong stakeholder engagement and a clear understanding of climate adaptation needs: CS2 (RiOMar) invested substantial effort in stakeholder work and recognised early that their communities needed tailored data —this is precisely the kind of engagement that T6.2 and T6.3 are designed to build upon. CS3 (Hamburg City) and CS6 (CCA Strategy) similarly showed active engagement with municipal stakeholders who have concrete adaptation decision-making needs. Close relationships with municipal stakeholders in CS3, CS4 and CS6 are a clear advantage for the upcoming work in T6.2, which requires continuous feedback from adaptation practitioners to ensure the FAIR2Adapt framework is applied in a way that effectively addresses their needs.

Other case studies will play different roles in Year 2. CS1 (Arctic Radioisotopes) will be more autonomous in applying the FAIRification framework—they can create FDOs with limited support from technical partners, making them an ideal champion for testing and improving the framework and providing early feedback from a community perspective. However, they have not yet meaningfully engaged with external stakeholders and the distinction between climate change science needs (understanding radioisotope distribution under different climate scenarios) and climate adaptation needs (supporting decision-making by Arctic communities and providing information on contamination risks for public officials and civil society) remains to be clarified. This distinction is fundamental to WP6's objectives: the project is not about producing better climate data, but about making climate-relevant knowledge actionable for the CCA community. CS4 (Portugal National Hub) is well-positioned to serve as an exemplary case study for both FAIRification and support of climate adaptation, combining technical capacity with clear understanding of how a national adaptation hub must serve adaptation actors.

These differences represent an opportunity for Year 2: case studies can learn from each other's strengths and help overcome bottlenecks already identified. CS1 and CS4 can champion the FAIRification framework and provide feedback to technical partners, while CS2's and CS6 stakeholder engagement experience can inform how other case studies approach their adaptation communities and local officials.

A significant lesson from Year 1 also concerns the relationship between technical partners and CCA communities. During the stocktaking and requirements phase, case study partners were often overwhelmed with technical questions about metadata schemas, FIPs, RO-Crate profiles, and semantic interoperability—questions they did not always know how to answer or, more importantly, how to relate to their case studies adaptation challenges. The flow of information was predominantly one-directional: technical partners asking communities to provide inputs that would feed into infrastructure development. This created a dynamic where communities felt like respondents rather than drivers of the process. Some case studies, such as CS2, CS4 and CS5, engaged directly with the technical WPs (2, 3 and 4) after struggling to visualize how FAIR would best support their

case studies. However, this engagement still lacks a proper structure (it can occur under specific 1-on-1 meetings or under recurrent WPs meetings) and driver (as a response to a concrete question or need from the case study).

The CS6 scope change demonstrated the importance of adaptive project management: external regulatory changes necessitated pivoting to a scope that ultimately provides better alignment with project objectives. The mapping of synergies with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC case studies revealed concrete opportunities for transfer case development.

What this enables next

Year 2 requires a fundamental shift in the relationship between technical and case study partners. **CCA communities must move from being recipients of FAIR solutions to owners of them.** This means:

- Communities take the driver seat in defining what problems need solving, with technical partners responding to these needs rather than the reverse. This requires a shift in paradigm for case study owners and will be supported by WP6.
- Case study partners do not merely adopt tools developed elsewhere but actively shape their evolution through continuous feedback.
- A genuine feedback loop is established where community experience with prototypes directly informs technical refinement in WP2, WP3, and WP4.
- Success is measured not by technical compliance but by whether solutions actually support adaptation decision-making

Year 2 will also **leverage champion case studies to accelerate learning across the consortium.** CS1 will be autonomous in applying the FAIRification framework—they can create FDOs independently (or mostly independently), freeing technical partners to focus support on case studies that need more assistance. CS4 will demonstrate the full pipeline from FAIRification to adaptation decision support, serving as an exemplar for both dimensions.

Four FAIR solution demonstrators will be presented at the General Assembly in March 2026, showcasing how the FAIRification framework connects to concrete case study needs. Each demonstrator leverages specific services from WP2, WP3, and WP4:

1. **FAIR Solution 1 (CS2 RiOMar):** Data processing pipeline for coastal water quality modelling
 - 1.1. *Purpose:* Enable regridding of simulation output to another grid (DGGS-Healpix), FAIRify it, and integrate in a STAC catalogue—overcoming the limited accessibility and usability of model data
 - 1.2. *Services:* STAC catalogue integration, DGGS Healpix-geo regridding, visualisation of DGGS-regridded datasets, RO-Crate profiles, I-ADOPT for

- oceanographic variable descriptions, P4A visualisation platform, EGI DataHub for large-scale storage (to prepare regriding data pipeline)
2. **FAIR Solution 2 (CS3 Hamburg City):** FAIR GIS workflow for urban climate risk assessment
 - 2.1. *Purpose:* FAIRify the software (GIS pipeline to generate the risk assessment maps) to create a workflow that can easily be reused in CS6 for the City of Bremen and/or transfer cases to produce risk maps—demonstrating cross-case replicability
 - 2.2. *Services:* Investigate the use of Galaxy workflow engine, GitHub repository with Codemeta + SOMEF metadata extraction, WorkflowHub registration, Zenodo publication, RO-Crate packaging
 3. **FAIR Solution 3 (CS3 Hamburg City):** Knowledge production from scientific publications
 - 3.1. *Purpose:* Make scientific claims and workflows verifiable and reusable for other researchers who wish to reuse knowledge or build upon similar methods. This solution can be directly applied in CS4.
 - 3.2. *Services:* Metadata extraction service (topics, keywords, entities), scientific claims extraction and verification, I-ADOPT variable descriptions, ROHub publication, RO-Crate with enriched metadata
 4. **FAIR Solution 4 (CS4 Portugal National Hub + CS5 weAdapt):** Literature review and extraction pipeline
 - 4.1. *Purpose:* Compare manual vs. LLM-based extraction and create machine-readable systematic reviews using the TIB Knowledge Loom—outcomes uploaded to weAdapt to benefit the global adaptation community
 - 4.2. *Services:* PRISMA framework with nanopublication templates, ExpertAI content extraction, automated vs. manual extraction comparison, RO-Crate packaging, Knowledge Loom integration

The selection of these demonstrators reflects project learning from Year 1. CS1 was not selected because they can FAIRify autonomously—the demonstrators focus on case studies where technical partners will work collaboratively with communities through the Helpdesk (T5.4) to show the concrete benefits of FAIR for adaptation decision-making. The FAIRification work will be performed primarily by technical partners as part of the Helpdesk task, in close collaboration with communities who guide requirements and validate results. The demonstrators were chosen based on:

- **Feasibility:** Achievable outcomes within the project timeline, leveraging services reaching alpha release at M15 (MS3.2 Alpha release FAIR Services) and integration in ROHub at M18 (MS2.3 FDO services integrated to ROHub - version 1)
- **Demonstrating FAIR value:** Making tangible the benefits of FAIRification for adaptation practitioners who struggled to see relevance during Year 1
- **Replicability:** Each demonstrator serves as a template—GIS workflow (FAIR Solution 2) is explicitly designed for transfer to CS6, extraction pipeline (FAIR Solution 4) benefits CS5 weAdapt directly

Critically, these demonstrators are designed not just to deliver what case studies initially requested, but to “stimulate imagination” and foster engagement (of both case study owners and technical teams). We believe FAIR can enable far more than what CCA communities currently envision. By showing concrete, working solutions, the demonstrators aim to trigger new questions: "If this is possible, what else could we do?" For instance, once CS4 sees how the extraction pipeline can automatically structure adaptation knowledge from systematic reviews, they may realise similar approaches could link their national hub to Climate-ADAPT or enable cross-border comparisons with Spanish adaptation strategies. Once Hamburg sees their GIS workflow registered in WorkflowHub and reused by Bremen, they may imagine a European network of cities sharing urban climate risk methods. The goal is to move communities beyond their initial requirements toward possibilities they (and the technical teams) had not considered—linking datasets that were previously siloed, enabling queries they didn't know they could ask, or supporting decision workflows they hadn't imagined. The demonstrators are a starting point for dialogue, not an endpoint for delivery.

The demonstrators will also serve as training material for the Helpdesk, enabling WP5 to support remaining case studies in replicating successful approaches.

T6.2 will continue testing FAIR2Adapt services for FDO creation across all case studies, but with communities leading the evaluation of what works and what doesn't. T6.3 (starting M18) will leverage the CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC synergies to develop transfer cases. MS6.3 (M20) will deliver the 2nd set of case study workshops, designed to put communities in the lead and can serve as test-beds for FAIR2Adapt services. MS6.4 (M21) will hold the first meeting for future uptake via EU Mission. MS6.5 (M24) targets confirmation of 2 transfer cases with Mission Adaptation signatories. D6.2 (M36) will document proof-of-concept applications, and D6.3 (M36) will report on uptake activities via EU Mission and EOSC.

3.6 WP7 - Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation

Lead: ALPHA | Status: On Track

WP7 establishes the project's visibility, stakeholder engagement, and strategic partnerships. The work package comprises three tasks: T7.1 General Communication and Dissemination (Lead: TIB), T7.2 Stakeholder Engagement (Lead: FT), and T7.3 Cooperation and Synergies (Lead: FT).

What was done

WP7 focuses on communication, dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and building strategic partnerships. Key achievements include:

- **T7.1 – General Communication and Dissemination:**

D1.3 – First Project activity, including Governance report

- MS7.1 achieved (M1): FAIR2Adapt branding completed. For the project logo, font, and identity, the work was initiated before the official start of the FAIR2Adapt project and was done with the EOSC Association and supervised by TIB. As a result, the FAIR2Adapt branding fully aligned with EOSC requirements to ensure visibility as an EU project under the EOSC umbrella.
- MS7.2 achieved (M3): Project website launched at fair2adapt-eosc.eu. The website includes sections on consortium, External Advisory Board, case studies, tools and resources. News, interviews, and press releases are regularly posted and disseminated via social media.
- D7.1 delivered (M6, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.16900738](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16900738)): Dissemination and Communication Plan, detailing project identity, website, social media content strategy, and the full communication plan for the project duration.
- Conference participation: EGU (April 2025) with poster on Arctic radioisotope modelling, presentations of the FAIR2Adapt project and I-ADOPT framework; EGI Conference (June 2025) with presentation, poster, booth, and elevator pitch; ECCA 2025 with organised session on "FAIR data and Open science in support of CCA"; SIGIR 2025; EOSC Symposium 2025 (Brussels, December 2025).
- **T7.2 – Stakeholder Engagement:**
 - Preliminary work for D7.4 (M18) Business Plan and Exploitation Strategy has begun
 - Market assessment and competitive landscape analysis initiated
 - Value chain and value proposition assessment for FAIR2Adapt's potential commercial offer underway
 - Main market trends related to the climate adaptation data market identified
- **T7.3 – Cooperation and Synergies:**
 - MS7.3 postponed (M8 → M15): Technical Working Group on CCA data management. FTC led preparatory activities by scoping options within the existing Climate Services TWG in cooperation with the MIP4Adapt Community of Practice. A comprehensive screening of FAIR-related projects via CORDIS (~2,200 projects) identified ~30 highly relevant initiatives. In December, the proposal received formal approval from MIP4Adapt, with the TWG launch planned for February 2026.
 - Strategic partnership with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC established, including: Joint Stakeholder Forum for CCA engagement (active until 31 December 2028); contribution to the TWG on FAIR for CCA data management, making this working group a joint endeavour; joint dissemination activities for EGI Conference 2025 and ECCA 2025. Collaboration will be strengthened in 2026 through participation in our respective GAs, and by planning more hands-on activities around FDOs and CCAs.
 - EOSC Symposium 2025 participation provided strategic insight into CCA community positioning within the emerging EOSC Node architecture. The second wave of EOSC Node enrolment presents an opportunity for dedicated CCA representation.

What we learned

Effective communication requires adapting messages to different stakeholder categories while maintaining consistency with project branding. The joint workshop with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC at the EGI Conference demonstrated the value of cross-project collaboration and helped identify synergies for transfer cases. Engaging consortium partners in content creation requires ongoing coordination and clear guidelines.

Participation in the EOSC Symposium 2025 (Brussels, December 2025) revealed strategic considerations for CCA community positioning within the emerging EOSC Node architecture. The CCA community is inherently cross-disciplinary, spanning environmental science, biodiversity, urban planning, public health, and economics. This presents both challenges and opportunities:

- Node positioning: CCA requires engagement with multiple EOSC Nodes rather than single alignment
- Thematic node opportunity: Second wave of EOSC Node enrolment raises questions about how CCA communities can ensure their needs are addressed within the evolving EOSC architecture. It may also be an opportunity for dedicated CCA representation
- Technical alignment: Project outputs being aligned with EOSC Interoperability Framework

The delay in MS7.3 (TWG establishment) from M8 to M15 reflects the need for thorough stakeholder consultation and alignment with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC. The additional time allowed for proper scoping within MIP4Adapt structures and secured formal approval and joint leadership, resulting in a stronger foundation for the TWG.

What this enables next

Year 2 will shift from establishing infrastructure to disseminating concrete results as technical WPs deliver outputs. The FAIR solution demonstrators presented at the GA (March 2026) will provide compelling content for communication activities.

The joint TWG with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC on FAIR for CCA data management will launch in February 2026, creating a sustained mechanism for cross-project coordination and community engagement. D7.4 (M18) will deliver the first issue of the Business Plan and Exploitation Strategy. D7.2 (M24) will report on dissemination activities, EOSC engagement, and EU Mission collaboration.

Communication will increasingly highlight case study achievements and demonstrator outcomes. Coordinated presence is planned at EGI Conference 2026, EOSC Winter School 2026, EOSC Symposium 2026 and ECCA (2027). The hybrid final event is planned for M34-M35, and 6+ webinars and video content are planned to expand reach.

Year 2 will require strategic positioning within the EOSC ecosystem. This means reaching out to other thematic communities, understanding how CCA intersects with existing and emerging EOSC Nodes, and identifying pathways to ensure CCA communities get what they need from the EOSC architecture. Both FAIR2Adapt and CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC outputs will be essential to demonstrate CCA community readiness and needs.

4. Governance Activities

4.1 Governance Structure Implementation

The FAIR2Adapt governance structure has been fully implemented as defined in the Grant Agreement:

- **Project Management Office (PMO):** Operational with one representative per beneficiary, serving as the ultimate governing body
- **Executive Board Meetings (EBM):** Bi-weekly on Mondays at 12:00-13:00 CET with the Project Management Team (PMT).
- **Work Package Leaders:** All 7 WPLs appointed and active

4.2 General Assemblies

Four General Assembly meetings were held during Year 1:

Table 4: General Assembly Meetings

Meeting	Date	Type	Key Decisions
Kick-off	13-15 January 2025	Ordinary	Project launch, initial planning, CS2 workshop
GA #1	26-27 May 2025	Ordinary	Regular 6-month review, progress assessment
GA #2	28 October 2025	Extraordinary	Vote on adding LifeWatch ERIC as partner (APPROVED). Vote on the subcontracting effort for SEI Oxford to carry out development work on the MAIA taxonomy (to become a key ontology for CCA).
GA #3	24 November 2025	Extraordinary	Approved Simula withdrawal and transfer of full coordination to LifeWatch ERIC

4.3 Key Governance Decisions

Decision 1: Addition of LifeWatch as partner

D1.3 – First Project activity, including Governance report

Approved unanimously on 28 October 2025 to enable Anne Fouilloux to continue technical coordination following her departure from Simula. This decision was superseded by Decision 3 below following Simula's withdrawal decision. Status: Pending EC approval of Grant Agreement amendment.

Decision 2: Subcontract for SEI-Oxford taxonomy work

Approved unanimously on 28 October 2025 to support technical development of the "MAIA" taxonomy, identified as a key resource for the Climate Change community.

Decision 3: Withdrawal of Simula and transfer of full coordination to LifeWatch ERIC

Approved unanimously on 24 November 2025 following Simula's decision to withdraw from the consortium. All coordination responsibilities (Administrative, Financial, and Technical) will transfer to LifeWatch ERIC. Timeline: Simula withdrawal letter to EC in December 2025; Grant Agreement amendment process in January 2026. Project activities continue uninterrupted during the transition.

4.4 External Advisory Board

The External Advisory Board (EAB) was established by M2 (MS1.2), comprising renowned experts:

- **Lorand Szentannai** - Senior Adviser at Sigma2 AS (Norway)
- **Kati Mattern** - Project Manager of Climate Change Adaptation at European Environment Agency (Denmark)

The EAB is gender-balanced and will meet annually online, with additional meetings when requested by the PMO.

EAB Engagement in Year 1

During Year 1, EAB members received periodic updates on project progress through the project newsletter and website. Formal EAB consultation meetings were not convened during Year 1. The consortium prioritised foundational activities—including stakeholder workshops, capacity building delivery, and technical infrastructure setup—which needed to mature before strategic external advice could be most effectively sought. Additionally, the consortium transition in Q4 2025 (coordinator departure and Simula withdrawal) required significant management attention, temporarily limiting capacity for advisory engagement.

Year 2 EAB Engagement Plan

The consortium recognises the importance of leveraging EAB expertise and has defined a clear engagement plan for Year 2:

- **Q1 2026 (by M15):** Invite the EAB to our next GA (March 2026) to review Year 1 outcomes, the four FAIR solution demonstrators, and provide them direct exposure to case study progress and consortium dynamics. We hope this will trigger strategic guidance on community engagement approaches
- **Q2 2026 (M18):** EAB consultation on the Business Plan and Exploitation Strategy (D7.4) and policy briefing priorities (D1.6)

- **Q3-Q4 2026:** EAB input on transfer case selection and EU Mission uptake strategy (T6.3)

4.5 Task Forces Established

Cross-WP task forces were established as flexible coordination mechanisms to facilitate collaboration across work packages:

- *Case Study Needs Identification Task Force* (Lead: Barbara/GFF)
- *Metadata Task Force* (Lead: Raul/PSNC)
- *Data and Knowledge Integration Task Force* (Lead: Markus/TIB)

During Year 1, the Case Study Needs Identification Task Force was particularly active, reflecting the project's initial focus on understanding stakeholder questions, requirements, and use-case contexts. The Metadata and Data and Knowledge Integration Task Forces were intentionally established early but are expected to become more active in Years 2 and 3, in line with the planned progression from needs elicitation to technical implementation and integration.

While these task forces were created with the flexibility to be activated earlier if needed, they are not formal governance or reporting structures. Rather, they serve as lightweight coordination mechanisms to ensure effective and smooth collaboration across WPs. For this reason, activities are reported within the relevant WPs rather than as standalone task-force outputs.

5. Quality, Risk and Ethics Management

5.1 Quality Assurance

Quality assurance procedures have been implemented as defined in the Project Handbook (D1.1):

- Deliverable review process operational with internal reviewers assigned (have not taken part in the writing of the deliverable)
- Half-yearly performance reports reviewed by Project Coordinator
- Quality indicators monitored and corrective actions applied when needed
- All quality-related documentation stored in project's collaborative environment

5.2 Risk Management

The full risk register containing 14 identified risks is documented in D1.1 Project Handbook (Section 4.3.2) and reviewed regularly during Executive Board Meetings. The table below summarises the status of key risks that were most relevant during Year 1:

Table 5: Risk register

Risk	Status	Mitigation Action
Coordinator withdrawal	MATERIALIZED and MITIGATED	Simula decided to withdraw from the consortium. Mitigated by: (1) GA approval to transfer full coordination to LifeWatch ERIC, (2) Anne Fouilloux continues as Technical Coordinator at LifeWatch as partner and transferring coordination.
Communities not understanding FAIR	Active	Demonstrator of FAIR solutions planned by March 2026 to show value to communities.
Stakeholder engagement challenges	Monitored	Design thinking workshops and regular stakeholder meetings implemented successfully. Contributing to the Stakeholder Forum that was set up by our sister project CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC.
Technical integration complexity	Monitored	Cross-WP task forces established to coordinate technical development.
Insufficient stakeholder engagement for FAIRification	Monitored	Year 1 workshops showed varying readiness; demonstrators planned
Difficulty testing through real-world case studies	Monitored	CS6 pivoted; other case studies progressing
Data privacy/security during FAIRification	Monitored	GDPR compliance maintained; no issues reported

5.3 Ethics and Compliance

No ethics issues have been reported during Year 1. The project maintains compliance with:

- GDPR and data protection regulations
- EU AI Act requirements - AI use limited to anonymized data for metadata extraction
- Open Science and FAIR principles as outlined in the Data Management Plan

Stakeholder workshop participants provided informed consent for data collection. Personal data collected during case study workshops is stored in accordance with the Data Management Plan (D1.2). No personal data has been shared outside the consortium. AI services deployed in the project (metadata extraction, I-ADOPT automation) operate on anonymised data only, with no high-risk AI applications as defined by the EU AI Act. AI-generated outputs are reviewed by human experts before publication.

6. Milestones and Deliverables Status

6.1 Milestones Status (M1-M12)

Table 6: Milestones Status

MS	Title	Due	Actual	Status
MS1.1	Project kick-off meeting	M1	M1	✓ Achieved
MS7.1	FAIR2Adapt Branding	M1	M1	✓ Achieved
MS1.2	External Advisory Board	M2	M2	✓ Achieved
MS5.1	FAIR Awareness course	M2	M2	✓ Achieved
MS5.2	Helpdesk Guide online	M2	M2	✓ Achieved
MS7.2	FAIR2Adapt Web platform	M3	M3	✓ Achieved
MS6.1	1st CS workshops	M3	M3	✓ Achieved
MS3.1	FAIRification API spec	M6	M6	✓ Achieved
MS5.3	FIPs published	M6	M6	✓ Achieved
MS5.4	SIPs	M6	M9	Moved & achieved
MS6.2	Case studies started	M7	M7	✓ Achieved
MS7.3	TWG CCA data mgmt	M8	M15	Postponed
MS5.5	Metadata v1	M9	M9	✓ Achieved
MS4.1	Knowledge Services spec	M10	M10	✓ Achieved
MS2.1	RO-Crate profiles	M12	M12	In progress to be achieved as planned e.g. by the end of December 2025.

6.2 Deliverables Status (M1-M12)

Table 7: Deliverables Status

Del	Title	Due	Lead	Status	DOI
D1.1	Project Handbook	M3	SRL	✓ Submitted	10.5281/zenodo.15130761
D1.2	Data Management Plan	M6	SRL	✓ Submitted	10.5281/zenodo.16901205
D7.1	Dissemination Plan	M6	TIB	✓ Submitted	10.5281/zenodo.16900738
D3.1	FAIRification framework	M12	UPM	In progress; to be submitted by 31st December 2025	10.5281/zenodo.18110239
D5.2	User Requirements	M12	GFF	In progress; to be submitted by 31st December 2025	10.5281/zenodo.18110626
D6.1	Stocktaking report	M12	SEI	✓ Submitted	10.5281/zenodo.18017945

D1.3	First Activity Report	M12	SRL	This document; to be submitted by 31st December 2025	10.5281/zenodo.18110818
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7. Deviations and Corrective Actions

7.1 Minor Deviations

MS5.4 - Semantic Interoperability Profiles (SIPs): This milestone was moved from M6 to M9 as communities needed to complete FAIR Awareness training before meaningfully defining semantic interoperability requirements. Following D5.2 recommendations, FIPs and SIPs have been aggregated into single extended FIPs at the case study level, rather than maintaining them as separate artefacts. This decision streamlines the approach and avoids duplication, as semantic interoperability considerations are best addressed within the same framework as other FAIR implementation choices. The extended FIPs now serve as the basis for more specialised FIPs at the digital object level. This has no impact on the overall project timeline.

MS7.3 - TWG on CCA data management: Postponed from M8 to M15 to enable proper coordination with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC on the joint Technical Working Group. The additional time allowed for thorough stakeholder consultation, comprehensive screening of FAIR-related projects via CORDIS, and securing formal approval and joint leadership within MIP4Adapt structures. The TWG will launch in February 2026. This delay results in a stronger foundation for the TWG and avoids duplication of effort.

CS6 Scope Change: Case Study 6 was adapted from its original focus on business climate risk assessments for CSRD sustainability reporting to FAIRification of municipal climate adaptation strategies, now partnering with the City and State of Bremen. This adjustment responds to changes in the EU regulatory landscape (CSRD/OMNIBUS) that reduced business demand for climate risk assessments. The revised scope provides stronger alignment with municipal adaptation planning, the EU Mission on Adaptation, and creates synergies with CS4 (both involve translating grey literature into machine-readable formats).

7.2 Significant Changes

Consortium change: Simula withdrawal and LifeWatch addition

Simula Research Laboratory has withdrawn from the consortium and has been replaced by LifeWatch ERIC. This change requires formal amendment to the grant agreement. The following actions are planned:

- Part B will need to be revised to reflect LifeWatch's role, contributions, and budget allocation

- Task responsibilities previously assigned to Simula will be reorganised to ensure smooth transition
- LifeWatch staff will be onboarded with direct support from the project coordinator (Anne Fouilloux), facilitating rapid integration into ongoing activities
- Impact assessment for deliverables and milestones involving former Simula contributions is underway

8. Outlook for Next Period (M13-M24)

8.1 Key Dependencies

- GA amendment approval (expected Q1-Q2 2026) — required to formalise consortium changes and budget transfers;
- Alpha service releases at M15 enabling integration for March 2026 demonstrators;

8.2 Impact Targets for Year 2

- Progress toward 50 multidisciplinary FDOs (project target)
- Contributions toward 14 scientific publications and 10 organised workshops
- 2 transfer cases confirmed with Mission Adaptation signatories (MS6.5, M24)

8.3 Key Upcoming Milestones

- MS2.2 (M15): Data and knowledge search and discovery service v1
- MS3.2 (M15): Alpha release of FAIR Supporting Services
- MS4.2 (M15): Alpha release of Knowledge Services
- MS6.3 (M20): 2nd set of Case studies workshops
- MS6.4 (M21): 1st meeting for EU Mission uptake

8.4 Key Upcoming Deliverables

- D3.2 (M18): FAIRification services description
- D5.3 (M18): 1st release of Customised CCA-related Services
- D1.6 (M18): First Policy Briefing
- D7.4 (M18): Business Plan and Exploitation Strategy Issue 1
- D1.4 (M24): Intermediate Project Activity Report
- D5.1 (M24): Community Capacity Building Report

9. Conclusions

FAIR2Adapt has successfully completed its first year, establishing the technical, methodological, and community foundations for FAIR-enabling climate change adaptation. The project is on track with only minor deviations managed without impact on overall objectives.

Year 2 must shift from "understanding FAIR" to "using FAIR"—with communities as owners of solutions, not respondents to technical questions. The four FAIR solution demonstrators at the General Assembly (March 2026) will be the first concrete test of this approach.

Key Achievements

- 13 of 15 milestones achieved on schedule (87% completion rate)
- 5 of 7 deliverables submitted, with 2 additional deliverables on track for submission by end of December 2025
- All 6 case studies launched and actively engaged with stakeholder communities
- Governance structures fully operational despite significant consortium transition
- Strategic partnership with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC established, including Joint Stakeholder Forum

These achievements contribute toward the project's impact targets, including 50 multidisciplinary FDOs, 14 scientific publications, and 10 organised workshops.

Key Challenges Identified

- Gap between technical FAIR infrastructure development and community understanding of practical benefits
- Need to shift from communities as respondents to communities as owners of FAIR solutions
- Varying levels of technical readiness and stakeholder engagement across case studies

Critical Success Factors for Year 2

- Successful demonstration of FAIR value through four solution demonstrators at the March 2026 General Assembly
- Timely completion of the Grant Agreement amendment process to formalise consortium changes
- Transition from FAIR readiness to FAIR in practice across all case studies
- Launch of the joint Thematic Working Group on CCA data management with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC